

Review Article

Nanotechnology in Targeted Drugs Delivery System: A New Horizon in Cancer Treatment

Snehal Thonge*¹, Anushka Thonge²

¹ Godavari Institute of Pharmacy, Kolpa, Latur, Maharashtra

² Pharate Patil College of Nursing, Pune

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 26 Sept 2025

Keywords:

Nanotechnology; Targeted drug delivery; Cancer therapy; Nanocarriers; Chemotherapy; Personalized medicine

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17205226

ABSTRACT

Cancer treatment is often limited by non-specific toxicity and drug resistance. Nanotechnology offers site -specific, controlled drug delivery using nanoparticles (NPs). This paper highlights types of nanocarriers, their mechanism, advantage, limitations, and future prospects in oncology.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer = Major global health challenge.

Limitations of conventional chemotherapy :

Systemic toxicity , low bioavailability , multi-drug resistance.

Nanotechnology : Emerging tool for precise, targeted therapy.

Aim of Paper : To discuss the role of nanotechnology in targeted cancer therapy.

TYPES OF NANOCARRIERS IN CANCER DRUG DELIVERY

- Liposomes** - biocompatible, approved formulation (e.g., Doxil® for breast/ ovarian cancer).
- Polymeric nanoparticles** - controlled release, biodegradable.
- Dendrimers** - branched polymers, high drug -loading capacity.
- Gold nanoparticles** - drug delivery + photothermal therapy.

*Corresponding Author: Snehal Thonge

Address: Godavari Institute of Pharmacy, Kolpa, Latur, Maharashtra.

Email ✉: snehalthonge61@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

- e) **Magnetic nanoparticles** - external magnetic targeting .

MECHANISM OF TARGETED DELIVERY

Passive targeting : Enhanced permeability & retention (EPR) effect in tumor tissues.

Active targeting : Ligand/ receptor binding (e.g., folic acid, antibodies).

Stimuli-responsive systems : pH, temperature, enzymes or light trigger drug release.

ADVANTAGE OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN CANCER THERAPY.

- Higher drug concentration at tumor site.
- Reduced systemic toxicity .
- Possibility of combining therapy + imaging (theranostics) .
- Controlled & sustained release.

LIMITATIONS/ CHALLENGES.

- High cost of development.
- Stability & scalability issues.
- Potential toxicity of some nanomaterials.
- Regulatory hurdles for clinical approval.

RECENT ADVANCE & EXAMPLES.

- FDA - approved nano formulations
 - Doxil® (liposomal doxorubic)
 - Abraxane® (albumin-bound paclitaxel).
- Research focus: personalized nanomedicine CRISPR- nanocarrier combination, immune-nanoparticles.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVES

- Integration of AI + nanomedicine for personalized cancer therapy.
- Development of multifunctional nanocarriers (drug + gene + imaging).
- Clinical translation from lab to large-scale production.

CONCLUSION

Nanotechnology holds great promise in targeted cancer therapy.

Although challenges remain , ongoing research & innovation will likely make nanomedicine a mainstay in oncology.

REFERENCES

1. Alexis, F. et Nanoparticle technologies for cancer therapy. *Nat Rev Drug Discovery*.
2. Peer, D. et al. Nanocarriers as an emerging platform for cancer therapy. *Nat Nanotechnology* .
3. Wang, A Z. et al. Nanoparticle delivery of cancer. *Anna Rev Med*.
4. FDA database of approved nanomedicine.

HOW TO CITE: Snehal Thonge, Anushka Thonge, Nanotechnology in Targeted Drugs Delivery System: A New Horizon in Cancer Treatment, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 9, 3116-3117. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17205226>

